

Sodium chlorite has also been used for the estimation of phenol and amines by using it as a bromometric reagent. Quantitative bromination method for the determination of phenol was described by Koppeschaar (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1875, 15, 2531). Paul and Singh (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 328, 605; 1955, 32, 599, 736) have used chloramine-B and potassium metaperiodate as bromometric reagents for the estimation of various inorganic ions and organic compounds. Bromine required in the present work for bromination was obtained according to the equation,

and by this method 2:4-dinitrophenol, *m*-nitrophenol, phenol, *p*-chlorophenol, anthranilic acid, *m*-nitroaniline, *p*-chloroaniline, *o*-nitroaniline and thiourea have been quantitatively estimated, following the method outlined by Paul and Singh (*loc. cit.*).

In the determination of 8-hydroxyquinoline, the modification of Fleck, Green and Ward (*Analyst*, 1934, 59, 325) has been followed. Thus, many metals may be determined indirectly by precipitating their metallic oximates with 8-hydroxyquinoline from their salt solutions and the organic component of the oximate may then be determined bromometrically with sodium chlorite as usual.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY COLLEGE,
HOSHARPUR.

Received July 1, 1957.

[*Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Vol. 35, No. 4, 1958]

ON THE APPLICATION OF VORTMANN-FORBES REACTION TO ANTIMONY OXIDE AND THIOSULPHATE

BY R. V. IVER AND J. K. DWIVEDI

The reaction between antimony trioxide in alkali-lye and sodium thiosulphate was studied by Meyer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1498) and suggested as a clock reaction. Vortmann (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2307) found the reaction between antimony trichloride and sodium thiosulphate to correspond with that of arsenious acid. Venkateswarlu (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 291) confirmed the existence of a minimum period of induction in the arsenious acid-sodium thiosulphate reaction in acid medium. The present work was undertaken to ascertain the existence of a similar minimum period of induction in the antimony oxide and thiosulphate reaction in presence of acids.

Procedure.—The apparatus was thoroughly cleaned with chromic acid and perfectly dried. The chemicals used were of B.D.H. sample. Sb_2O_3 was exactly weighed out for normal solution and double the amount of tartaric acid was added, followed by water. The mixture was slightly warmed to obtain a clear solution,

The tartaric acid was neutralised by the addition of sodium bicarbonate. $N/2$ -Sodium thiosulphate and N -HCl were also prepared.

In a 250 c.c. conical flask Sb_2O_3 solution (25 c.c.) was taken, to which the necessary amount of water was added. In another 100 c.c. conical flask 20 c.c. of thiosulphate solution was measured out. The thiosulphate was then added to antimony oxide solution. The thiosulphate flask was washed with the requisite amount of water and added to the antimony oxide. Finally the N -HCl was added and the stop-watch started immediately. The flask was then thoroughly shaken and the time was noted when the first turbidity of antimony sulphide appeared. In each set the total volume was kept constant at 100 c.c. The results obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sb_2O_3 taken each time = 25 c.c.

Sodium thiosulphate taken each time = 20 c.c.

Water added.	Water for rinsing thiosulphate flask.	N -HCl and $N-H_2SO_4$.	Induction period for	
			HCl.	H_2SO_4 .
25 c.c.	20 c.c.	10 c.c.	430 sec.	265 sec.
20	20	15	283	172
20	15	20	178	116
15	15	25	105	76
15	10	30	58.8	69
10	10	35	47.2	58.5
5	10	40	68	102
5	5	45	98.5	146
5	5	50	126	180

From the results it is thus clearly established that there does exist a minimum period of induction in this reaction also. Further work is in progress.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
MADEHAV COLLEGE,
UJJAIN, M.P.

Received November 5, 1957.